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PROTECTING AND RESTORING BIODIVERSITY USING MAINSTREAM FINANCE

D6.1: Coordination of learning sites for BIOFIN-EU use case demonstrators

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Page | 1

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Executive Summary

The Purpose of the Deliverable

The BIOFIN-EU Learning Sites (LS) play a central role in the project and contribute to the research methodology during the activation phase of the project. The learning sites provide a wide range of real world examples of nature-based solutions (NbS) and ensure that the BIOFIN-EU outputs are relevant and impactful. We include a set of LS that represent best practice (exemplars) as well as innovative actions (explorers) and have potential contributions across multiple tasks described in the BIOFIN-EU description of action. This deliverable is intended to facilitate clear communication and coordination of the learning sites (LS) within the BIOFIN-EU consortium activities so that the research proceeds in an efficient manner. The deliverable additionally supports communication activities to external audiences as well as current and prospective collaborators.

Subject of the Deliverable

This deliverable is focused on providing a current view of the LS that are contributing to the project (updated from the original proposal), allowing BIOFIN-EU researchers to interact with the LS in coordinated manner and providing opportunities to align our research with activities taking place across other EU projects.

Summary

The BIOFIN-EU consortium's first plenary meeting (Month 6) included a workshop that focused on validating the LS potential contribution to the BIOFIN-EU objectives. The workshop design was highly interactive, and it initiated a process where consortium members could link LS with specific activity within the project's tasks across all work packages. This activity was followed up with further refinement of the workflow and technologies required to ensure that 1) LS could make a full contribution to the overall project, 2) planned collaborations with LS were streamlined and 3) BIOFIN-EU research results in a clear value proposition and does not unduly encumber LS with additional workload.

Main conclusions

The deliverable resulted in two main conclusions, namely, there is a need to **coordinate LS activity along high-level research themes** and it is important for the project objectives that we create a centralized system to manage interactions in a way that prioritizes **flexibility and transparency**.

Table of Contents

- 1. Introduction to Learning Sites in the BIOFIN-EU project.....7**
 - 1.1. Introduction to Learning Sites.....7
 - 1.2. The role of learning sites in the BIOFIN-EU project8
- 2. Interacting with the Learning Sites10**
- 3. Internal Coordination and Communication.....11**
 - 3.1. Flexibility and Transparency.....11
 - 3.2. Collaborative Technology.....12
- 4. Conclusion15**
- References.....16**
- Annex I – Learning Site Overview17**

List of Figures

- Figure 1 BIOFIN-EU Research Phases **Error! Bookmark not defined.**
- Figure 2 Managing Information flow 9
- Figure 3 LS Research Activity (Themes) 11
- Figure 4 Overview of LS Task Alignment 12
- Figure 5 Card’ showing typical detail of Research Activity 13
- Figure 6 Filter function to support LS Coordination 14

List of Tables

- Table 1 List of Learning Sites..... 9

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
LS	Learning Site(S)
NbS	Nature-based Solution
ES	Ecosystem Service(s)

1. Introduction to Learning Sites in the BIOFIN-EU project

1.1. Introduction to Learning Sites

This section will give an overview on who the learning sites are and the role of these learning sites in the BIOFIN-EU project. BIOFIN-EU have engaged ten learning sites to help to ensure that what we are building will achieve our goal of integrating NbS into decision making in mainstream finance. To follow is a summary on each learning site, categorised by country, with further details available for viewing in Annex 1 – Learning Site Overview.

LS# and Brief Intro	Location	Core Focus
LS#1 Waters of Life	West of Ireland	The Waters of LIFE aims to help reverse the deterioration of Ireland’s most pristine waters.
LS#2 Wild Atlantic Nature	West of Ireland	The project works with farmers and local communities to conserve and improve the quality of blanket bogs and associated habitats, and the ecosystem services they provide including clean water, carbon storage and biodiversity.
LS#3 NBS Governance Structures, Water Quality & Population Health	Pipiripau Basin, Brazil	NBS Action: Soil and road conservation; forest protection; use of sustainable technologies for agriculture and the rational use of water. Environmental education to the local population; revitalization of irrigation
LS# 4 Unlocking private finance to scale up local communities ES protection and restoration	São Paulo, Brazil	Cleaning, de-pollution and canalization of streams; ecosystem protection; urban drainage.
LS#5 Climate adaptation and risk mitigation using new financial instruments and business models	Pró Mananciais Program of State of Minas Gerais, Brazil	Spring protection, expansion, and consolidation of green areas; basin monitoring and evaluation; wildfire detection and suppression; and local environmental education.
LS#6 Standardising Public-Private Contracts and Data Sharing to Scale-Up Mainstream Finance	Lombardy Region (Italy)	Management and development of multifunctional forests for ecosystem services provision.

LS#7 Business model design to redirect financial flows for water conservation and water quality	Brenta River, Italy (LIFE Brenta Project)	Protect and restore Natura 2000 site
LS#8 Financial Innovation (Biodiv. Credits) - ES Impacts, Corporate Preferences and SFT Compliance	National Park Appennino Tosco-Emiliano, Italy	Development of ecosystem services for climate action and biodiversity
S#9 Finance for Urban NBS and Human Health	Mojmilo Urban Forest, Sarajevo	Development and extension of an urban forest that will produce co-benefits for biodiversity and human health.
LS#10 Finance for Urban NBS and Human Health	Malmö, Sweden	Nature restoration project near the city center of Malmö

Table 1 List of Learning Sites

1.2. The role of learning sites in the BIOFIN-EU project

The learning sites play an essential role within the BIOFIN-EU project. BIOFIN-EU has an ambitious agenda that is seeking to integrate NbS into decision making in mainstream finance. The learning sites provide the consortium with the opportunity to develop and test novel approaches in biodiversity and ecosystem services (ES) data capture, aggregation and analytics to help reduce transaction and reporting costs associated with biodiversity-linked finance. The learnings sites are expected to contribute to several of BIOFIN-EU's key objectives, including: **i)** To develop and test solutions able to record and share meaningful, reliable and useful biodiversity and ES data from heterogeneous and dispersed/scarce data sources with minimal delay and in the appropriate format, **ii)** To understand the preferences and regulatory requirements of capital owners, financial institutions and NBS-providers so that relevant governance aspects are designed into business models and financial instruments and associated enabling technologies and tools, **iii)** To develop trustworthy, accurate, and fair data sharing of biodiversity and ES outcomes to reduce transaction costs and other barriers to nature finance, **iv)** To design and test new business models and biodiversity-linked investments that maintain protections for NBS-providers and their communities while securing long-horizon benefits for NBS-promoters, **v)** integrate relevant processes, systems and reporting and disclosure requirements to help BIOFIN-EU support organisations in directing financial flows towards biodiversity protection and restoration, **vi)** To build knowledge and skills among current and future finance professionals and decision-makers, and build a community to advance the implementation of the regulations to co-develop solutions and accelerate the financial flow of funds towards biodiversity-linked activity.

BIOFIN-EU uses a **multi-actor** approach embedded within an overarching methodology of **co-design**; a collaborative practice that sees participants as experts in their own needs and experiences. BIOFIN-EU's multi-actor co-design methodology will be used to generate tools for *The NBS Dashboard* (WP2-5) and contribute to **policy recommendations** (WP6) relating to the SFT. The intention is to build knowledge and skills within the investment community through the *Impact Maximisation* (WP7) across all phases from data collation, through activation and replication to their integration into wider EU contexts. The BIOFIN-EU consortium itself is multi-actor in composition, including a diverse group of providers of nature-based solutions (ANNEX I comprises a description of the BIOFIN-EU learning sites), communications specialists (RAIN) and academic researchers (UL, QUB, UNIPD, UM, UG, COFAC).

The co-design approach is necessary since NbS are not currently a part of mainstream finance and BIOFIN-EU is addressing complexity in multiple domains (e.g. local ecosystems and communities as well as competitive market dynamics and technological limitations in the financial system). Therefore, the advancement of the planned research is unlikely to be linear. The involvement of the LS supports a thought process that is 'holistic' and helps us to tackle issues by 'first considering them in their entirety, including the broader context they derive from' (Dell' Eria et al, 2020).

Moving through the phases of research will involve the BIOFIN-EU consortium participating in a divergent, broadening phase of unexpected idea gathering and brainstorming, followed by a convergent phase in which the most promising ideas are selected and put into practice. While this approach is likely to lead to the best outcomes for the project, it also creates several risks if not coordinated effectively. For example, it may lead to duplication in information requests, over-extension of learning site resources, miscommunication in relation to the expected outcomes from a collaboration or delayed access to learning sites. The current deliverable provides a detailed view on how learning sites will be coordinated including a description of the workflow and technologies that will support research activities for the duration of the BIOFIN-EU project.

2. Interacting with the Learning Sites

Figure 1 provides a simple visual of the implicit phases of research undertaken within the BIOFIN-EU project with project tasks and related deliverables potentially spanning several phases. When task leaders and their research team are planning a specific area of research it may require the involvement of one or more LS. It is thus important to establish a protocol for engagement with LS and an effective mode of communicating planned activity with other consortium members.

Figure 1. BIOFIN-EU Research Phases

LS provide an important role in several phases of research (visualized in Figure 1). They can support the ‘creation of connections’ – providing links to scientists and communities delivering NbS as well as introducing existing actors within the financial system that support NbS. In Phase II, LS are important in providing connections to help understand the preferences of local populations and NbS providers and importantly in Phase III, the LS provide an essential environment for co-designing and testing new solutions for financing NbS. Phases I to III are not expected to proceed linearly, but rather consortium members will move forward and back between phases to identify those solutions that can be most effective in re-directing finance towards the protection and restoration of nature.

Work package meetings provide an opportunity for individual researchers to identify prospective research and decide on how to integrate LS to contribute to this research. During this initial planning phase, the *Task Leader* connects with the *LS Contact Person* to discuss the planned research. This connection is typically facilitated directly with the support of the work package leader, and it can also be facilitated or moderated by the BIOFIN-EU project manager.

Figure 2. Managing Information flow

3. Internal Coordination and Communication

3.1. Flexibility and Transparency

The BIOFIN-EU research is exploratory by nature, this necessitates flexibility in how we advance our research. It also requires modes of working that maintain transparency in relation to the research topic under investigation as well as the research that is planned for the upcoming period.

The BIOFIN-EU approach is to identify gaps in the existing SFT and provide a unifying digital technology (The NBS Dashboard) for integrating biodiversity and ES data into financial decision-making. Data and evidence on NBS implementation and impact best practices (WP2) as well as economic valuation by NBS stakeholders (WP3) will be collated. Both activities will interact to ensure a constant exchange of information about potential options to be used in each learning site during the activation phase.

To streamline internal communication, we provide a categorization of LS research activity across four themes (Figure 3). This provides researchers with a project level view on how activity on individual tasks contributes to the overall project.

Figure 3. LS Research Activity (Themes)

These research themes are used within collaborative technology (described in 3.2).

Meeting Structure

Work package Meetings

Work package meetings take place monthly, and these provide an important venue where planning takes place for individual tasks. The work package leader guides the discussion, and the team identify where their research can engage with each of the LS and plan their engagement. The LS contact will be engaged at an early stage and the feasibility of the

engagement will be established. **Current and planned activity in relation to LS is then managed on a MS Teams 'board' (see 3.2) within the Learning Site channel.**

Leadership Team

The work package leaders meet on a bi-weekly basis (Tuesday am) to share current and upcoming research plans and identify linking research across WPs. This is supplemented by weekly virtual office hours (Friday am) which are intended to moderate the flow of one-to-one emails and ad-hoc conversations. It exists as a forum where WP leaders can informally discuss potential research opportunities, project risks, and identify and resolve knowledge gaps exist.

3.2. Collaborative Technology

Given the exploratory nature of the research, there is a requirement to maintain flexibility in the manner and timing of the research undertaken at each LS. This is facilitated through a dynamic 'board' on MS Teams. This board (LS Task Alignment) is in the Learning Site channel on the project's MS Teams site. Within the board, each learning site is assigned as a 'bucket' within which specific research activities are described (by task and by theme) on individual cards. Each research activity is owned by the lead researcher who works with the task leader and LS contact point to ensure that the activity aligns with specific task outcomes and aligns with other activities associated with that LS.

Figure 4. Overview of LS Task Alignment

The board provides a transparent and flexible way to discuss activity.

Populating, editing and updating the 'board':

- **At the end of each WP meeting** the board should be (i) shared onscreen and meeting participants agree LS activities as they relate to specific tasks.
- **During WP leader meetings** (i) the board provides an opportunity to view and discuss specific research actions related to LS
- **LS contacts and research leads** can undertake ad-hoc editing and query specific tasks (e.g. synchronizing activities in relation to their LS), discussing changes with collaborators.

Each card contains details on specific activities. They are labelled by 'task' and 'research theme'.

When completing each card, it is important to input scheduling and priority level as well as some detail on the activity underway or planned.

Figure 5. 'Card' showing typical detail of Research Activity

There are several coordination features available on the board. These can be used to support communication in meetings, identify where there may be a mismatch between activity and completion date for a specific task and ensure that LS activity is planned efficiently.

Figure 6. Filter function to support LS Coordination

4. Conclusion

This deliverable outlines the exploratory nature of the research being undertaken and the central role the LS plays in helping to advance this research. As a consortium, we have worked together to identify how best to operationalize this research and mitigate potential risks in relation to LS engagement including avoiding breakdown in information, creating systems to advance several distinctive research questions in an efficient way and maintaining LS proactivity and engagement with the BIOFIN-EU project.

We have created an efficient meeting structure at WP level and explicitly recognized that our research will iterate between different *phases* of research (design thinking approach). This has been communicated to all researchers in the consortium in early-stage meetings (Kick Off Meeting, M3; Plenary Meeting, M6 and WP Leader Meetings). To support this exploratory research, we additionally scheduled *free-form* workshops that enable researchers to ideate and explore aspects of our planned research so that they can be implemented effectively. A core element of the current deliverable is the development of the MS 'board' that records current and planned activities in relation to the LS. It will be important that this 'board' is maintained so that it reflects activities in real-time. For this to be effective, a review of the board will be embedded as part of all work package meetings under the agenda item: 'LS Activities: Review and Action Items'.

References

Dell’Era, C., Magistretti, S., Cautela, C., Verganiti, R., Zurlo, F. (2020) Four kinds of design thinking: From ideating to making, engaging, and criticizing. *Creativity and Innovation Management*.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/caim.12353>

Annex I – Learning Site Overview

LS#1 Waters of Life (Active)

Contact Point: Colas Chervier (UL)

Location: Ireland

NBS Action: Remediation, biodiversity protection and restoration. The Waters of LIFE is an EU LIFE Integrated Project (IP) which aims to help reverse the deterioration of Ireland’s most pristine waters. The ongoing loss of high-status waters is among the most concerning, protracted and persistent water quality trend in Ireland. Other water quality trends have well-understood cause and effect, with detailed plans in place to mitigate impacts. More actions are necessary to protect pristine waters. Many of these waters are small, upland streams. The protection and restoration of these waters is one of the key underpinning principles of the Water Framework Directive. The overall objective of the Waters of LIFE IP is to support the implementation of measures to protect and enhance High-Status Waters and thus to support the work of the Blue Dot Catchments Programme.

BIOFIN-EU Contribution: We have identified several activities aimed at enhancing the design of the result-based payment scheme (RBPS) implemented by WoL: (i) We will conduct a baseline study to evaluate the impact of RBPS on individual non-pecuniary motivations to restore nature and on social capital in commonly-owned lands. (ii) We will provide recommendations to the WoL program to finalize the RBPS design and possibly anticipate farmers' responses to these economic incentives. (iii) We will conduct experiments to test alternative RBPS designs, such as introducing a collective bonus and/or a bonus for ecological score increase, along with exploring complementary payment flows linked to the financial sector (discounts on loans or insurance products).

LS#2: Wild Atlantic Nature (Active)

Contact Point: John Garvey (UL)

Location: Ireland

NBS Action: Wild Atlantic Nature is an exemplar LS. It is a 9-year EU-funded LIFE Integrated Project that works with farmers, local communities and landowners to add value to the wide range of services provided from our Special Area of Conservation (SAC) network of blanket bogs and associated areas. These peatlands provide clean drinking water, store carbon, support biodiversity, produce high quality food and support resilient rural economies and livelihoods through farming, tourism, recreation and other activities. As part of the project, a pilot voluntary Results Based Payments Scheme (RBPS) will be linked to the quality of the habitat.

BIOFIN-EU Contribution: WAN is an example of a successful publicly funded project that has developed expertise, local knowledge and trusted networks within local communities. We are examining the barriers (governance, operational, financial instrument design) that prevent these successful projects from scaling up their activities. WAN and BIOFIN-EU are exploring potential mechanisms that can be used to unlock mainstream finance to increase the scale of these activities. BIOFIN-EU and WAN lead investigators have drafted prototypical financial instruments that have been shared through public channels (Department of Environment, Climate and Communications and the National Treasury Management Agency as well as through a financial services firm, to better understand investor requirements and design features for a sustainability-linked bond.

LS#3: Pípiripau Basin, Brazil

Location:

NBS Action: Soil and road conservation; forest protection; use of sustainable technologies for agriculture and the rational use of water; environmental education to the local population; revitalization of irrigation channels; monitor projects' actions, water quality and quantity data.

Context: Since 1997, there have been several initiatives in Brazil that cover the creation of schemes to finance water quality and related ecosystem services, from soil conservation to flora protection support actions.

Challenge: Individual or legal entities must maintain, restore, or improve the environmental conditions of ecosystems. This is funded by up to 0.2% of the water and wastewater utility (concession) operating revenue (from tariffs), as well as financial contributions from other entities.

Data Sources (COFAC): This LS provides BIOFIN-EU with data underlying costs and outcome data (ES, public health, economic activity, economic preferences, and valuations)

that will be a useful benchmark when designing equivalent private finance models. Historical data on NBS selection will also inform which procedures and related criteria (and descriptors) worked, and those that did not.

BIOFIN-EU Contribution & Target Users: BIOFIN-EU will examine the design and implementation of funding models and their associated governance structure to identify their effectiveness in supporting water quality and the potential pathways for private finance. BIOFIN-EU will extract design principles from LS2 to understand decision-making priorities, monitoring costs and potential transaction size for utilities and large corporations who could act as NBS-providers.

LS#4: Unlocking private finance to scale up local communities ES protection and restoration

Location: São Paulo, Brazil

NBS Action: Cleaning, de-pollution, and canalization of streams; ecosystem protection; urban drainage.

Context: The promoter is the municipal government, and activity is funded via 7.5% of the water and wastewater utility gross revenue (from services), budget appropriations; income from the Fund's assets; donations, reimbursements, or subsidies. This provides a relevant case that highlights both the added value in unlocking financial flows, and the opportunities for improvements/ recommendations, namely covering the governance structure of those funding schemes and their financing sources.

Challenge: To unlock finance, there is a requirement to understand NBS cost-benefits, to inform risk analysis and enable a more transparent mechanism to define “who should” and “how to” finance the fund.

Data Sources (COFAC): This LS follows LS2 and provides rich different urban or rural-urban actions, which provide BIOFIN-EU with data on costs and outcomes (ES, public health, economic activity, economic preferences, and valuations) that will also be useful to benchmark equivalent private finance models. LS3 will also provide data on the interaction with other urban planning areas such as Housing, with earmarked initiatives used to minimise harmful downstream impacts.

BIOFIN-EU Contribution & Target Users: LS2 and LS3 provide examples of the NBS-funding schemes deployed in utilities. They will provide initial use-cases for understanding data and governance requirements to activate private finance, how communities can be recruited and incentivised to protect and restore biodiversity.

LS#5: Climate adaptation and risk mitigation using new financial instruments and business models

Location: Pró Mananciais Program of State of Minas Gerais, Brazil.

NBS Actions: Spring protection, expansion, and consolidation of green areas; basin monitoring and evaluation; wildfire detection and suppression; and local environmental education.

Context: LS4 provides BIOFIN-EU with an explorer NBS that is activated by the regional utility (COPASA) and implemented by local communities.

Challenge: The program aims to improve the quality of water in the locality through environmental diagnosis and implementation of solutions designed to improve water management. The introduction of mainstream finance to increase water protection and restoration activity has the potential to be highly impactful on human health and freshwater biodiversity.

Data Sources (COFAC): Data on different governance structures (e.g., players, roles, implemented decision-making procedures), costs and the outcomes achieved (ES, public health, economic activity, economic preferences, and valuations). Specifically, LS4 will provide multi-level governance data and requirements.

BIOFIN-EU Contribution & Target Users: Co-design and validate 'Menu of Governance Options' within the *Dashboard* and the analysis of Fund governance structures will help to shape the *Dashboard* to contribute to informed decision-making independence, conflict management, and transparency.

LS#6: Standardising Public-Private Contracts and Data Sharing to Scale-Up Mainstream Finance

Contact point: Anna Biasin (ETIFOR)

Location Lombardy Region **NBS Actions:** Management and development of multifunctional forests for ecosystem services.

Context: This explorer NBS directly tests approaches to valorisation of ecosystem services and the design of business models and financial instruments. ETI provides technical assistance to organisations interested in participating in the Lombardy Region's BioClima call for proposals. Applicant project proposals will have to predict, measure, and certify the expected impact on ecosystem services.

Challenge: Co-design and testing of accessible data sharing capability as well as tools to facilitate participation in a public-private partnership (PPP) is a necessary first step if private

finance is accessed. ETI activity includes the delivery of independent third-party verification of ecosystem services, using the Forest Stewardship Council® (FSC®) standard.

Data Sources (ETI): Qualitative data (FSC® certification and the Ecosystem Services Procedure, FSC-PRO-30-006 V1-0) as well as established quantitative data measurement, independent verification and valorisation of ecosystem services will be available to BIOFIN-EU.

BIOFIN-EU Contribution & Target Users: Activities to identify existing bottlenecks for mainstream finance. In addition to the expected impact on ecosystem services, BIOFIN-EU provides access to potential NBS-promoters (corporate and financial institutions) via DEL and ILSI. This will create the opportunity to design and test governance and contractual arrangements that provide the enabling conditions for SFT adoption.

LS#7: Business model design to redirect financial flows for water conservation and water quality

Contact point: Anna Biasin (ETIFOR)

Location: Brenta River, Italy (LIFE Brenta Project) **NBS Action:** Protect and restore Natura 2000 site **Context:** The LIFE Brenta 2030 project responds to the problems of lack of governance and financing and to the environmental impacts of drinking water abstraction in the Middle Brenta area (Northern Italy). **Challenge:** NBS uses water pricing to promote good governance through planning, participation and development of an effective governance system, while implementing a pilot funding mechanism for water resource and biodiversity conservation through water pricing. **Data Sources (ETI):** Economic valuation (quantitative) and governance structures (qualitative) data will be available to the BIOFIN-EU. Datasets comprise outputs from the analysis of impacts and pressures on and by the Integrated Water Service, the definition of NBS measures that could prevent such impacts, and the integration of the costs associated with such measures into the drinking water tariff. **BIOFIN-EU Contribution & Target Users:** BIOFIN-EU will extend from the methodologies set up and applied in the LIFE Brenta project to identify the infrastructure required to increase the scale of private financing. This will consider; NBS categorisation, streamlining of data sharing capabilities and creating close alignment with the reporting requirements of the SFT.

LS#8: Financial Innovation (Biodiv. Credits) - ES Impacts, Corporate Preferences and SFT Compliance

Contact point: Anna Biasin (ETIFOR)

Location: National Park Appennino Tosco-Emiliano, Italy **NBS Action:** Development of ecosystem services for climate action and biodiversity **Context:** With the support of CREA (the network of research institutes depending from the Italian Ministry of Agriculture, Food Sovereignty and Forests) and University of Milan, **a standard for the sustainable management of forests** with the provision of carbon sequestration and biodiversity protection services has been developed by the National Park Appennino Tosco-Emiliano's authorities. After being **certified under FSC and PEFC**, some forests of the NP have been additionally certificated for the additional improvement of biodiversity through changes in the regeneration system. A Registry has been created by the National Park technical services.

Challenge: Sales of the **credits to industrial companies** in 2022 demonstrates the need to improve metrics and the mechanism of payment, checking the consistency of the system of payment with the new standards that will be defined through the CRC Regulation implementation. **Data Sources (ETI):** Quantitative and qualitative data from 2022 auction of biodiversity credits and well as Historical pricing of biodiversity credits and NP registry data. LS7 will provide data for the application of Voluntary Biodiversity Credits (VBCs) integration with FSC ES Pro to allow potential investments in the conservation and/or enhancement of biodiversity of these areas.

BIOFIN-EU Contribution & Target Users: LS7 will be used to **understand risk-valuation considerations** and the **design of financial instruments with co-benefits** (e.g. carbon sequestration, habitat creation, ES for recreation,..) as well as opportunities to aggregate and centralise the delivery channel for private finance. BIOFIN-EU will contribute to a proof-of-concept sustainability credits system that includes quantified benefits on biodiversity.

LS#9: Sarajevo

Contact: Asmir

Location Mojmilo Urban Forest, Sarajevo **NBS Action** Development and extension of an urban forest that will produce co-benefits for biodiversity and human health.

Context: The **CONNECTING Nature Horizon** project aimed to strengthen the policy and practices necessary to scale up urban resilience, innovation, and governance via nature-based solutions. Mojmilo Urban Forest is one planned outcome from this project.

Challenge: Integrate private finance into NBS solution that reduces air pollution and increases amenity value.

Data Sources (SERDA): IoT and Sensor output capturing ES services data; health and activity data; participation and recreation data linked to NBS development.

BIOFIN-EU Contribution & Target Users: BIOFIN-EU will co-design, test and validate a novel financing instrument. Private finance (e.g. private insurer) will be deployed to maintain and expand the urban forest, where the amount paid is benchmarked to ecosystem services data measured by sensors (air quality, sound, and light pollution) and related to human health outcomes. The design and implementation will follow **a local One Health approach that is collaborative, multisectoral and transdisciplinary**. The **NBS Dashboard** will centralise access to IoT sensor data and facilitate the transmission of private capital to extend and develop the urban forest.

LS#10: Malmö

Contact point: Eleni Lampi

Location: A harbor area in the Malmö city, in the Southern part of Sweden

Malmö municipality's project aims to boost biodiversity and encourage the return of vanishing species, focusing on eelgrass, vital as a breeding ground for juvenile fish. They are pioneering a natural re-wilding approach in Sweden for seabed restoration by allowing nature to spontaneously recover, anticipating the eelgrass to regrow independently. Another option which will be explored is cultivating eelgrass beds, which is costlier yet yields quicker results. **Context:** The Malmö harbor is an experimental project for other city areas in the future and a distinctive kind of project in various aspects. It is a site where human activity has ruined the environment and wiped-out biodiversity but where the city has chosen to clean up and improve the environmental quality at the same spot where the harbor operations have harmed it. **Challenge: The Malmö municipality have an interest in exploring re-wilding by letting the environmental improvements happen in a natural way without any human involvement** (after the sand-capping and reduced water depth). This is cheaper than active restoration, but more uncertain and it takes time. They need to collaborate with researchers, but they also need more information about re-wilding. Although rewilding is cheaper, funds are needed. In particular, if this is to be scaled up. Right now, **the municipality plans to fund this through taxes**. But there is an interest in other financial solutions, including money from sales of land/residential development around the area. Some people involved are rather knowledgeable but **would like to know more about what is happening at both the national and EU-level when it comes to**

biodiversity policies. Data Sources (UGOT): Surveys to a random sample of individuals living in the region Skåne (region where the city of Malmö is located).

BIOFIN-EU Contribution & Target Users: The aim with this project is to investigate individuals' preferences for restoring the harbor area and increasing the level of biodiversity through eelgrass beds. In addition, we investigate the importance of time of restoration, i.e. how important it is for people to have a fast recovery of biodiversity. This is important for several reasons, not the least for the choice between re-wilding or actively planting eelgrass beds.

